

Optimized Length Design and Construction of 3 Ton Lifting Capacity Diesel Forklifts

Halil ÇETİN

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture,
Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University, Burdur, Turkey

Abstract : In general, forklifts perform loading and unloading operations in very narrow, closed or open areas. Therefore, it is necessary to increase maneuverability by shortening the forklift length. For this purpose, the production of forklifts with shorter lengths compared to similar diesel forklifts with a capacity of 3 tons was designed. For this purpose, 3D design studies were carried out. In order to shorten the chassis, the forklift fenders and steps were made in one piece. In addition, significant structural changes were made to the counterweight and its length was shortened. Our new model, whose production has been completed, is among the models with the shortest length among similar diesel forklift models of the same capacity, with its 2590 mm L2 length. These features allow the forklift to operate in very small spaces. Abstract. In this study, forklifts with shorter lengths than similar diesel forklifts with a capacity of 3 tons were designed and manufactured. For this purpose, 3D design studies were carried out to shorten the forklift length. Appropriate material selection was made to ensure driver safety and chassis durability. Forklift fenders and steps, which were our original work during production, were made as a single piece in order to shorten the chassis. Additionally, significant structural changes were made to the counterweight and its length was shortened. Our new model, whose production has been completed; With its 2590 mm L2 length, it is among the shortest models among similar forklifts.

Key words: Maneuverability, Forklift Length, Lifting Capacity

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the working areas of forklifts are generally places such as warehouses and warehouses, there is not enough space for the forklift to work in such areas. In addition to the fact that it is very difficult for a forklift to load and unload in such narrow and small spaces, the time allocated for the operation is also quite long. On the other hand, since the driver using the forklift has great difficulty in maneuvering, unwanted accidents may occur during the maneuver. For these reasons, it has become essential to increase the maneuverability of the forklift by shortening its length without reducing its lifting capacity. In order to shorten the forklift length, it may be possible to optimize the chassis length, and therefore the forklift length, by first changing the location and dimensions of the chassis, chassis components, counterweight, and parts such as steps and mudguards. Before starting work on this issue, diesel forklifts with a lifting capacity of 3 tons should be well known. Forklifts generally consist of parts such as chassis parts, load lifting and counterweight and auxiliary units. The most important parts that directly affect the forklift length are; counterweight, steps and fenders. In order to manufacture a forklift with a short length and turning radius, but high lifting capacity and maneuverability, 3D surface and mechanical designs were first made. A literature review was conducted on forklift modeling[1] and chassis studies[2].

Forklift shortening operations were made on fenders, steps and counterweight. For this process, unlike other forklift models, the fenders and steps were manufactured as a single piece. In order to shorten the length of the counterweight without changing its center of gravity, gaps of different geometries were opened at the top. Figure 1.1 below shows our KFD30 model, with forklift parts and chassis assembly completed. Significant changes and improvements were made to the chassis members and counterweight to shorten our prototype model.

Figure 1.1 Schematic representation of characteristic quantities in the KFD30 Forklift.

For diesel forklifts, characteristic sizes are given in Table 1.1 below. Among these dimensions, our subject of review will be the L2 forklift length.

Table 1.1: Characteristic quantities included in the KFD30 Model.

Titling Angle	α/β	Forward/Backward	Degree
Mast Height, Lowered	h 1	2-Stage Mast	mm
Std. Free Lift	h 2	2-Stage Std. From Ground	mm
Std. Lift Height	h 3	2-Stage Std. From Ground	mm
Mast Height Extended	h 4	2-Stage Mast	mm
Height Overhead Guard	h 6		mm
Lenght, with Std. Forks	L 1		mm
Lenght, to Fork Face	L 2		mm
Width, at Tyre	b 1	Single	mm

Forks	s/e/l	ThicknessxWidhxLenght	mm
Widht, Fork Carriage	b 2		mm
Ground Clearance	m1	Under Mast	mm
	m 2	At Center of Wheel Base	mm

In order to shorten our prototype model, significant changes and improvements were made to the chassis members and counterweight. The center of gravity of the prototype model designed and built within the scope of the project was found.

II. CHASSIS SHORTENING WORKS

In order to shorten the chassis, dimensional design studies were first carried out on the forklift footboards, fenders and counterweight. In the design studies, the chassis and its components were dimensioned and strength values were found using the Solidworks program.

2.1 Changes Made on the Chassis

As seen in Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2, by making the forklift steps and front and rear fenders in one piece, the chassis length will be shortened and the forklift length will also be shortened. On the other hand, as seen in Figure 2.3, the counterweight placed on the rear axles behind the chassis takes up significant space on the chassis, so the length of the counterweight must be shortened. Therefore, taking into account the effect of the counterweight on the center of gravity of the forklift, its height was increased and its length was shortened, without changing the center of gravity.

Figure 2.1: Monolithic forklift steps and rear fenders

Figure 2.2: Monolithic front

Figure 2.3: Notches on the Upper and

Lower fenders

2.2 Changes to the Counterweight

In order to shorten the truck length, significant changes were made to the counterweight. Since the height of the shortened counterweight would increase, the upper parts of the counterweight were evacuated in order to prevent the center of gravity from changing. In this way, the center of gravity was pulled downwards. As the length of the counterweight becomes shorter, the counterweight length must be optimized to prevent the driver's visibility from decreasing with increasing height. In order to perform the optimization process, attention should be paid to the center of gravity of the forklift while increasing the height of the counterweight. The optimization process is done by unloading the upper parts of the counterweight. In this way, the counterweight whose upper parts are emptied will also increase the driver's field of vision, which is very important for preventing accidents and driver safety. Therefore, utmost attention should be paid to the driver's visibility when unloading the upper part of the counterweight. Figure 2.4 below shows the counterweight with its upper part emptied, as a result of the design studies.

Figure 2.4 Forklift counterweight

2.4. Comparison of the Length of Our Model and Other Forklift Models

By manufacturing the fenders and steps as a single piece and shortening the counterweight length, the length of the forklift was shortened. In our prototype model, the length L2 between the lifting chuck and the outer end of the counterweight is shorter than in other similar forklift models. The L2 lengths of our KDF30 Model and other forklift models [3,4,5][6,7],[8,9],[10,11],[12] were examined in detail. Table 2.1 gives the L2 lengths of our model and other diesel forklift models with a lifting capacity of 3 tons. As seen in Table 2.1 above, among 3 Ton capacity forklifts, our KDF30 model is among the shortest forklift models with its L2 length.

Forklift Mark	Forklift Model	Country	Forklift L 2 length (mm)
KARABAL	KFD30	T.C	2590
HYSTER	H2.0- 3 OFT	USA	2633
DOOSAN	DG30NXP	BE	2665
CLARK	C30D (Europe GmbH)	D	2668
LTMG	LTMG FD30	CHINE	2682
KOMATSU	FD30-17, FD30HT-17	JP	2705
STILL	STILL RX 70-30	D	2702
DOOSAN	D30S-9	GB	2730
TAILIFT	PFD30-3.300	TW	2760
TOYOTA	TOYOTA FD30	SE	2765
LINDE	LINDE H30D	D	2800

III. FORKLIFT ASSEMBLY

Before assembling the forklift chassis elements, chemical analysis of the materials used in the construction of the chassis, elevator and safety cabin must be carried out. Table 3.1 includes the analyzes and reasons for the materials to be used in the manufacturing of forklift components. Completed forklift components; Taking into account the analysis reports, they were mounted on the forklift.

3.1. Material Analysis Used in Forklift Chassis, Load Lift and Cabin Manufacturing

Table 3.1: Forklift Chassis, lift and Safety Cabin, material analysis

Experiment/ Test or Analysis name	Test reason	Test type	Test Site	Results
Spectral analysis of the steel plate used in cabinet manufacturing.	Cabin safety material selection	Spectral analysis	TSE Çayırova Campus Machinery Laboratory.	In accordance with the required standard norms and operator work it is safe.
Spectral analysis of cabin construction profiles.	Appropriate material selection for cabin safety.	Spectral analysis	TSE Çayırova Campus Machinery Laboratory.	In accordance with the required standard norms and operator work it is safe.
Forklift Chassis Material	forklift safety	Spectral analysis	TSE Çayırova Campus Machinery Laboratory.	It complies with the required standard norms. Chassis material is a suitable choice for carrying the system.
Forklift Lift Material	forklift safety	Spectral analysis	TSE Çayırova Campus Machinery	Required standard norms and Material suitable for lifting the load has been selected.

			Laboratory.	
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IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Considering that the forklift working areas are very narrow, as a result of the studies, significant changes were made to our model in order to shorten the forklift length. Unlike other diesel forklift models, the steps and fenders were made in one piece. To prevent the center of gravity from changing, gaps were opened in the upper parts of the counterweight. With all these changes, it was possible to produce our model with a 2590 mm L2 forklift length, 11 cm shorter than the closest similar forklift model. Short and compact forklifts are preferred in places where working areas are very narrow. Our forklift is manufactured for this purpose. However, where work areas are suitable, larger capacity and powerful forklifts can be used if necessary.

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